

FORMATION OF READINESS FOR SELF-DEVELOPMENT OF MORAL CHARACTERS IN PRIMARY CLASS PUPILS AS ONE OF THE ASPECTS OF MORAL EDUCATION

Qaytarova Nargiza Kaxramonovna

TSPU basic doctoral student named after Nizomi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7685465>

Abstract. *It is also the task of general education schools to educate children who are formed in terms of education in modern life. Therefore, in this article, the formation of preparation for the self-development of moral qualities in elementary school students was considered as one of the aspects of moral education. And accordingly, the statement of opinions was reflected in the content of the article.*

Keywords: *moral education, moral qualities, preparation for self-development, social requirements, moral culture, elementary school students, degradation.*

At the current stage of society's development, the moral person is one of the most important values, which determines the social requirements for educational institutions and the need to familiarize pupils with the system of moral values. It is known that, at the same time, modern education is based on a person-oriented approach. This means creating conditions for the development of a person. In this case, the task of education is to create a new system of values that helps to form the pupil's moral culture, to form a person oriented to humanity. Moral qualities are formed in children from a young age.

The problem of moral development of primary school students is of particular importance due to the lack of community spirituality, the alienation of a person from culture as a way of preserving and transmitting values, which leads to a change in the understanding of good, and evil in the younger generation leads society to moral decline puts the danger of meeting in front of him.

Formation of moral qualities of primary school teachers is one of the most difficult tasks of education in the conditions of a modern educational institution. However, teachers note an increase in students' aggression, cruelty, emotional deafness, self-isolation and self-interest. The problem of moral education is becoming more and more urgent, especially now, when cruelty and violence are common. In this regard, choosing different methods of educating the moral qualities of a person and using them wisely is one of the main tasks facing teachers at all levels, especially in general education institutions.

Modern pedagogic literature is not missing from the collection of literature studied in relation to scientific work. It is in modern pedagogical literature that moral education of a person is considered as the ability to purposefully form a system of moral relations and improve them and create new relations. Moral education of pupils is effective only as an integral process of pedagogical organization of the whole life of schoolchildren, formation of their ideas and concepts.

One of the tasks of moral education is to prepare elementary school students for the self-development of moral qualities of an individual, especially in modern society, when the behavior of some adults around them contradicts moral values. Moral education, designed to answer the question of how to live with dignity, is contrary to the norms and rules of modern life. Pupils cannot resist external influences, cannot resolve internal contradictions and conflicts, begin to

adapt, which contributes to the degradation of their personality. In order to survive socially and spiritually, a growing individual must be able to act and act in an ever-changing world without losing his identity, moral principles, or self-respect. As a result, in order to understand the problem posed at the beginning of the article, some stages of moral education are briefly considered.

The development of moral education as a scientific theory in various world literatures dates back to the 18th and the first half of the 19th century. The teachers of the 18th century put forward the idea of social education and suggested building the whole process on the basis of virtues and examples. For example, I.I. Betskoi in his brief instructions defines the moral qualities that should be formed at school: compassion, simplicity, love for one's neighbor, generosity, noble national pride, moderation, gentleness, arrogance and away from what is called self-love. E.B. Sireyshchikov said: "How difficult and how important moral education is, because the well-being of not only families, but the whole society depends on it."

As the formation of preparation for self-development of moral qualities in elementary school pupils is considered as one aspect of moral education, it is an effort to recognize students and regulate their actions, taking into account the characteristics of each of them; to teach students to act according to their desires, not motives; encourage students to act for good and noble causes; teach to determine the consequences of one's actions; teaching to harmonize position and pleasure; advance notice of passing the test; encouraging students to learn using other people's examples and behaviors is a task that requires a lot of attention.

It should also be said that in the studied literature, it is possible to observe thoughts close to the idea of educating a citizen who seeks to change living conditions. It can be seen that moral education is dependent on mental education, because it helps a person to choose between different motives, develops the ability to understand life observations. Mental processes (analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization) are also involved in the formation of moral concepts, so the more moral the mental powers, the more perfect the moral concepts. But a number of scientists also attach great importance to feelings, because ideas can motivate a person to act only if they are supported by feelings (love of the country, sense of brotherhood, self-appreciation, deep respect for a person, truthfulness, honesty and sensitivity, sympathy). He looks for human morality not in a collection of knowledge, but in a group of emotions that correspond to the soul. At some stages of the development of pedagogical thinking, the problem of the technology of moral formation arises. In their works, scientists recognize the unity of physical, mental and moral education and try to cover the process of moral education from birth to adulthood. At the same time, it is worth noting that it is necessary to pay attention to the primary school of general education.

Studying the stages of the development of the theory of moral education shows that representatives of education and training follow the ideas of "non-violent pedagogy". They considered "freedom" to be the leading principle of education and upbringing, through this principle they understood the non-violent influence of one person on another person to form moral habits and personal characteristics in an educated person. According to scientists, moral qualities are characteristic of children from birth, for example: truth, kindness, beauty, humanitarianism, but under the influence of the environment, the child changes for the better. Therefore, it is not wrong to see the main task of education in helping to create a highly creative person who can be the creator of an ideal society. It is no secret that the goal of moral education is defined as the education of aspirations in a person that can turn him into a tireless fighter. Setting pupils free and providing all positive information at their disposal for the development and disclosure of all

inactive creative forces can be called the first steps in the development of will through free movement in elementary school students.

REFERENCES

1. Андреев, А. А. Знания или компетенции? Текст. / А. А. Андреев // Высшее образование в России. 2005. - № 2. - С.3 -11.
2. Беляева, А. П. Тенденции развития профессионального образования Текст. / А. П. Беляева // Педагогика. 2003. - № 6. - С. 21-27.
3. Весна, М. А. Самоорганизация студенческих сообществ с различной целевой направленностью Текст. / М. А. Весна. Курган: Из-во Курганского государственного университета, 2004. - 272 с.
4. Volovikova, M.I. Axloqiy ideal haqidagi rus g'oyalari / M.I. Volovikov. - M .: Rossiya Fanlar akademiyasining Psixologiya instituti, 2012 yil.
5. Shuvalov, A.V. Mehribonlik saboqlari / Katynskaya E.A., Shuvalov A.V. // Maktabdagi tarbiyaviy ishlar. O'quv ishlari bo'yicha direktor o'rinbosari biznes jurnali. - 2011. - 7-son. – 76-75-betlar.
6. <https://cyberleninka.ru>
7. <https://infourok.ru>
8. <https://shkolyariki.ru/uz/>
9. <https://yspu.org>
10. <http://window.edu.ru/>
11. <https://docs.google.com>
12. <https://www.dissercat.com>
13. <https://natural-sciences.ru/ru>